

Development and implementation of integrated curriculum in vocational colleges

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Abstract:The integration of theory and practice course is a teaching method based on students' ability development, which organically combines theory learning and skill training. The development and implementation of integrated curriculum is conducive to the cultivation of double-qualified teachers, the improvement of teachers' scientific research level and the effective improvement of teaching quality. Vocational colleges can effectively implement integrated courses by means of enterprise research, organizing expert interviews, establishing professional digital resource database, and developing integrated course standards, teaching materials and teaching places. In the process of implementing the integrated curriculum, attention should be paid to the following aspects: the improvement of teachers' comprehensive ability, the improvement of teaching equipment and sites, the compilation of working pages and the weak theoretical foundation of students, etc. In addition, it is also necessary to establish a multi-level integrated curriculum evaluation system, innovate and reform the evaluation methods, contents and forms in order to improve the teaching evaluation quality of vocational colleges.

Key words: Integration, Integration of truth and reality, The curriculum reform

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China is in the era of globalization with rapid development of economy and science and technology. Information, intelligence, network and cloud big data have

become the core words of today's social development. Enterprises' demand for talent quality has greatly increased. Vocational colleges should be based on the development of the practical need of society, enterprises and students, innovative talent training mode, quicken the development of integrated curriculum, and better stimulate students' interest in learning, improve the students' professional ability, employment level, effectively improve the school quality of teaching, so as to better serve social and economic development. The implementation of integrated curriculum in vocational colleges is conducive to the organic combination of students' theoretical learning and skill learning, and to the significant improvement of teachers' theoretical level and enterprise practical ability, so as to build a high-quality "double major" student team and "double professional" teacher team.^[1] The development and implementation of integrated curriculum is not the work of one or two teachers. It requires the joint efforts of all the faculty members, from the top down, from enterprises to schools, from teachers to students. The guidance layer should play the navigation role, the organization layer should play the pivotal role, the development layer should play the backbone role, and the implementation layer should play the subjective initiative. The school needs to extract typical work tasks and make work pages according to the needs of the enterprise. Teachers prepare lessons collectively, discuss teaching methods and conduct classroom teaching. When problems arise in teaching, teachers in turn continue to carry out enterprise research, modify typical work tasks and revise work pages, which is a cyclical and tortuous process of progress.

The primary school of Nursing and Preschool Education of Shougang Technician College aims at promoting students' ability development, Schools should further develop and implement integrated curriculum, combine students' learning interests, assign students work tasks integrating theoretical learning and practical skills, let students experience their professional roles in real work situations, and greatly improve their post adaptability and comprehensive professional accomplishment.

I.The characteristics of integrated curriculum

With the continuous change of teaching methods in vocational colleges, the integrated curriculum reform has become an important content promoted by the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security of China. The education and teaching methods in vocational colleges are undergoing a significant change, and talent cultivation is developing towards a more diversified direction. Under the background of integrated curriculum reform of vocational colleges, teachers and students of vocational colleges should adapt to the development and implementation of integrated curriculum as soon as possible, and give full play to the role of integrated curriculum in personnel training and social development. The Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security "opinions" put forward that we should further promote the integration of vocational colleges in the course of the development and implementation, innovate the training mode of vocational colleges, attempt to establish a national professional standards as a minimum standard, to work as a talent training guide, pay attention to cultivate the students' comprehensive professional quality, establish integrated curriculum teaching system. Integrated curriculum, that is, the combination of theory and practice in the training of students' vocational ability teaching as a whole consideration, separate curriculum standards, through the implementation of each teaching link to ensure the realization of the overall goal. The integrated curriculum should aim at improving

students' comprehensive social ability and guiding them to "make progress in doing".

Teachers should mobilize the enthusiasm of students to study hard and practice more, make students change from "I want to learn" to "I want to learn", and cultivate students' teamwork spirit and comprehensive vocational ability. The integrated curriculum has the following characteristics:

1.Pay attention to the integration of truth and reality

The integrated course conforms to the needs of the teaching reform and development of vocational colleges in today's society. It is a teaching method that gives consideration to both theoretical learning and practical learning. It is implemented through the alternation of the two, and effectively realize s the combination of school theory teaching and enterprise practice as well as the integration of "teaching, learning and doing".^[2]

2.Focus on students' ability development

Integrated course will develop students' ability in the core position, pay attention to students' core accomplishment and their professional skills. Through the clear, specific, operational task drive the teaching with vocational element, greatly stimulated the students' interest in learning and seeking knowledge desire, is advantageous to the students' practical ability, innovation ability, problem-solving ability and the development of good thinking quality and so on.

3.Integration of teaching, teachers, teaching materials and teaching sites

The characteristics of integrated curriculum are also reflected in the integration of teaching, teachers, teaching materials and teaching sites. Teaching integration refers to simultaneously carrying out theoretical and practical courses every week, presenting the course contents to students in the

form of work pages , and stimulating students' interest in learning with diversified teaching methods such as micro-lessons, videos and pictures. Teacher integration means that teachers can improve the level of integrated teaching by participating in the training of integrated courses. The integration of teaching materials means that students are required to complete the work pages efficiently and master the key knowledge according to the teaching outline and the important knowledge points in the teaching materials. The integration of teaching sites means that students can take turns to have classes in the classroom and the training room, and they can conduct practical skills immediately after acquiring theoretical knowledge.of teaching materials means that students are required to complete the work pages efficiently and master the key knowledge according to the teaching outline and the important knowledge points in the teaching materials. The integration of teaching sites means that students can take turns to have classes in the classroom and the training room, and they can conduct practical skills immediately after acquiring theoretical knowledge.

II. The value of integrated curriculum development and implementation

Through the development and implementation of the integration of course, not only teachers' teaching level has improved greatly, also stimulated students' learning enthusiasm in professional course. Students have deepened their understanding of professional theories by experiencing the role of preschool teachers in practice. Practice has proved that the effect of integrated teaching is remarkable. As soon as graduates arrive at their jobs, they can enter into the role and are deeply favored by employers. Therefore, schools and enterprises will have closer ties, which will bring brand effect to schools and enhance teachers' sense of honor in vocational schools. The students cultivated by integrated teaching meet the demand of the market and also expand the space for the future teaching of vocational colleges.

1.It is conducive to the improvement of teachers' level and the cultivation of double-qualified teachers

In the process of integrated curriculum development, teachers in vocational colleges can fully understand the standards of enterprises' demand for talents through in-depth investigation into enterprises, so as to better cultivate a batch of high-quality talents for social development. On the other hand, I can more intuitively grasp the physical and mental development characteristics of children of different ages, kindergarten care and education skills, and preschool education professional skills (piano, vocal music, dance, art, story telling, etc.), so as to become a qualified double-qualified teacher. To create opportunities for students to enter the enterprise practice, better develop students' vocational ability. Therefore, the development and implementation of integrated curriculum in vocational colleges is conducive to the improvement of teachers' professional and integrated teaching ability in preschool education.

2.It is conducive to improving teachers' scientific research level

Vocational college teachers in the development process of the integration of curriculum through combing research materials, writing business research report, and on this basis to develop the course standard and integrated teaching material, establish preschool education professional digital repository, make micro class, in turn, create integration fine courses, construct integrated training rooms. In the process of "doing", teachers can effectively master the diversified abilities that should be possessed by talents to meet the needs of enterprises and social and economic development, and their awareness of finding and solving problems, innovation ability and scientific research level are greatly improved.

3.Conducive to improving the quality of teaching

The development and implementation of integrated

curriculum in vocational colleges provides students with a lot of opportunities for practical teaching, so that students can have the opportunity to teach in front of real children. By assigning situational learning tasks, teachers guide students to learn, teach and make progress in doing, which greatly mobilize students' subjective initiative in learning and practice. In the discussion and communication with the group, the students have developed the teamwork ability, problem solving ability. Practical operation, playing, singing, speaking and jumping and other professional skills have been greatly improved. Students' practice in a real work situation is conducive to the comprehensive and sustainable development of their emotional attitude, cognition and skills. With the improvement of students' overall comprehensive quality, the teaching quality of the school has been greatly improved and its influence in the society has been gradually expanded.

III.Strategies for integrated curriculum development and implementation

The development and implementation of integrated curriculum is a strategic measure for vocational colleges to improve teaching quality, ensure employment placement and enhance core competitiveness. The development and implementation of integrated curriculum can organically combine theory and practice in course teaching, teach theoretical knowledge in skill operation, learn skills and abilities in task application, and finally improve students' vocational ability and cultivate qualified talents for enterprises and the society. In the development and implementation of integrated curriculum, innovative development strategies should be combined with the actual situation of vocational colleges .

1.Conduct enterprise research and build a perfect talent training system

The development of integrated courses in vocational colleges should be based on enterprises, and the development status of enterprises and the demand for talent quality should be understood through in-depth practice in the front line of enterprises. In the process of implementing integrated teaching, teachers should integrate the content of enterprise practice into professional theoretical teaching, make students master the principle of real integration teaching content, and provide enterprise practice opportunities for students, encourage students to apply what they have learned in school theory knowledge to real work situation, improve the students' adaptability and professional quality. Therefore, only based on enterprise research, vocational colleges can develop integrated courses that meet the needs of enterprise development, build a perfect talent training system, and train a group of high-quality skilled talents for social development.^[3]

2.Organize and hold interviews with experts in professional fields

Vocational colleges should organize a professional conference in the field of integrated curriculum development, inviting experts which have rich practical experience and curriculum development experience to participate in the meeting, discuss the integration of vocational education courses with typical cases of talent cultivation system, explicit integration course of talents cultivation target and the various stages of the teaching task, let the student to study the practice in the real work situations, so as to improve students' comprehensive vocational ability. After the meeting, experts' opinions and suggestions should be sorted out in time, and talents training objectives and implementation plans of the integrated course should be determined according to the actual development of students in the school.

3.Establish a professional digital resource base

Preschool education specialized development of integrated curriculum need to establish a professional digital repository,

mainly includes curriculum standard, micro lesson, teaching courseware, animation, video, image resources and typical case teaching, homework problem set, test, etc. These resources complied with the development of the social network, intelligent, is an important component of integrated curriculum.

4. Develop integrated curriculum standards and promote teaching implementation

Teachers in vocational schools should assign specific learning tasks with clear goals and strong operability according to the development of enterprises, basic education and the contents of modern vocational education. Through the rationalization description of the above learning tasks, the standard of the integrated curriculum is determined. During the implementation of the integrated curriculum, teachers should check the curriculum standards and adjust them timely according to the completion of students' learning tasks. Teaching is the embodiment of implementation teaching design intent. According to the "integration of mechanic college curriculum standard (trial)" requirement, teaching generally contain clear task (describe the task source, mission requirements, explains the necessary theory knowledge, students need to complete the task of receiving work), planning (students in the form of group work plan, clear division of tasks, implementation procedures, tools and materials required for the implementation of preparation), assessment plan (students will plan to submit a teacher assessment, and teacher assessment, guide to modify or approved after examination and review, so as to foster professional consciousness "which can implement after teacher's examination and approval"), the implementation plan (according to the plan, the student through division of labor, complete the micro-task implementation, inspection and debugging step by step, summary analysis (group consultation, summary of task completion, writing summary materials and reporting to the whole class), process control (in the implementation process, according to the evaluation

standards step by step, implementation process evaluation), and other six steps. According to the different tasks, the above steps can be flexibly selected to complete the design of teaching implementation. In the design process, in addition to cultivating students' professional abilities, students' social abilities and methodological abilities such as self-learning ability, ability to search for information, ability to summarize and express, ability to organize and coordinate, and ability to work in a team should also be fully considered.

5. Develop integrated curriculum materials

As a basic teaching tool, teaching materials are the basic guarantee for training high-skilled talents, which is directly related to the training of skilled talents needed by enterprises. According to the actual jobs demand in today's kindergarten, vocational colleges should break the boundaries between disciplines, develop integrated teaching materials that integrate theory teaching and practice teaching. The teaching units are designed according to the typical work tasks of the kindergarten, so as to realize the task-oriented teaching mode of the job working process and promote the organic combination of theoretical knowledge and skill training. The development and implementation of integrated curriculum also put forward new and higher requirements for teaching materials used in technical colleges. On the one hand, the integrated teaching materials should adapt to the modern vocational education system, and should give students more space for development. On the basis of the skills and knowledge required for the establishment of the major, several optional elective courses in different major directions are added. Now many vocational colleges are doing ordering cultivation mode of teaching. It means that the theoretical knowledge and skills that employers really need are put into teaching, which provides a broader space for the development of students in technical colleges. Students can freely choose the learning content according to their own characteristics and development needs, so as to provide security for students who want to further study. On the other hand, the teaching

materials should be compatible with the professional skill appraisal, the mechanic colleges and universities graduates is different from the ordinary university, both when they graduate to get school graduation certificate issued by the colleges, also issued by human resources and social security department of the professional qualification certificate, to the joining together of two card, which is one of the conditions of some units of choosing and employing people often as required when hiring. In combination with the professional setting of technical colleges, it is necessary to carefully study the national vocational standards, compile corresponding teaching materials according to the vocational standards and the level of vocational skill identification, and carry out teaching. The textbooks should be applicable to the basic knowledge of most technical college students, and the content should consider the students' cognitive characteristics, interests and abilities. To serve the development of skills, to serve the employment of students. With the development of times, the teaching materials should be innovative and go deep into the frontline of enterprises to discover, excavate and discuss the successful experience of front-line preschool teachers, and make full use of network resources to enrich the content of the teaching materials. Introduce new skills, new knowledge, new teaching methods and methods simultaneously in the teaching materials. Game skills of design, for example, imagine it is very simple, but in the actual operation one will encounter all sorts of practical problems, the design of the rules of the game and play a large amount of time to the accumulation of practice experience. Therefore, it is necessary to learn knowledge in practice, deal with the relationship between theoretical knowledge and practice, and realize the integration of theoretical teaching and practical teaching, the integration of ability cultivation and job docking, and the integration of practical training and on-the-job learning and doing.

6. Develop integrated course teaching places

According to the teaching practice, the traditional

teaching place should be adjusted and reformed in time so as to build a teaching place that can satisfy both theoretical teaching and practical operation. For example, to improve the existing traditional practical training places, creating both necessary classroom teaching blackboard, computer and projection equipment, and have enough to practice operating equipment and tools to perform the job, it provides guarantee for teachers' teaching and students' operation, ensures that theory and practice can be carried out alternately, and ensures the smooth implementation of integrated teaching. To improve students' interest in learning and meet the requirements of learning and work. For example, in combination with the actual situation, a small class with no more than 30 students and 2 theoretical and practical teachers are assigned to jointly organize and complete the project work tasks of integrated teaching. Teachers should keep abreast of the students' learning situation and adjust the teaching schedule in time to ensure the high quality of learning tasks within the prescribed time, so as to achieve good results in the integrated course teaching. The development of integrated curriculum in vocational colleges should build an integrated teaching place in line with the specialty characteristics, which can not only carry out theoretical teaching, but also carry out skill training, and integrate the theoretical teaching place and practice room. This kind of real working environment is conducive to students' flexible application of theoretical knowledge, experience the professional role of preschool teachers, and improve the comprehensive vocational ability of post demands.

IV. Issues that should be paid attention to in the course of integrated curriculum development and implementation

The integrated curriculum means that the content of learning is carried out in the work, and students realize learning through the work. Therefore, integrated curriculum reform is not the reform of one or two courses, but based

on this major, aiming at the requirements of enterprises for students of this major, and integrating the requirements of enterprises for students' quality and ability when integrating the courses of this major, so as to train students not only with skills, but also with the comprehensive quality and ability required by enterprises. Therefore, In the course of integrated curriculum development and implementation, attention should be paid to summarize experience in time to improve the quality of teaching. Vocational colleges should organize and hold teaching seminars regularly to summarize the problems in the process of integrated teaching in order to solve the problems in time and improve the teaching effect.

1.Higher requirements are put forward for teachers

The implementation of integrated curriculum puts forward higher requirements for teachers' scientific research level, professional knowledge, professional ability and physical quality. First of all, the integrated curriculum development requires teachers to have a high level of scientific research, and teachers are required to develop a set of integrated teaching materials suitable for the development needs of enterprises and the characteristics of the development of students in our school, and according to the integrated teaching materials, develop the teaching outline, teaching plan and work page. During the implementation of the integrated curriculum, teachers should change their educational concepts, focus on students' ability development, mobilize students' work enthusiasm, and guide students to actively learn, participate in discussions, negotiate to solve problems and cooperate to complete learning tasks in real work situations. Secondly, the integrated curriculum puts forward higher requirements on teachers' professional competence and comprehensive quality, requiring teachers to adopt diversified teaching methods, such as group cooperation method, carousel method, partner jigsaw method, etc., so as to effectively stimulate students' enthusiasm and interest in work and improve students' professional self-confidence and sense of achievement. Finally, the integrated curriculum puts forward

higher requirements on teachers' physical quality, requiring teachers to design work pages and prepare play and teaching AIDS for students to practice skills, to constantly supplement theoretical knowledge and go deep into the frontline of enterprises for practical training, and to fully prepare lessons and correct homework on time.

2.Higher requirements are put forward for teaching equipment and venues

In the implementation of the integrated curriculum, students should make full use of the integrated textbooks and the contents of the professional digital resource database for independent learning. The learning effect of students depends on the perfection of multimedia equipment and the integrity of teaching site. Therefore, the integrated curriculum puts forward higher requirements for teaching equipment and site.

3.Writing work pages is of high difficulty

The integrated course adopts the form of work page for teaching. The writing of work page plays an important role in the integrated course. It needs to pay attention to the following aspects. First of all, the work page should take into account the actual development of students and the requirements in the curriculum standards and curriculum syllabus. Secondly, the working page should integrate theoretical knowledge with enterprise practice. Finally, the job page should take into account the company's employment standards and students' interests. ^[4]

4.The key point is to stimulate students' interest in learning because of their weak theoretical foundation

Vocational college students like hands-on practice, they have weak theoretical basis, lack of interest in theoretical knowledge. On the one hand, the implementation of integrated curriculum requires practical skills training and on the other hand, theoretical knowledge learning. If students'

theoretical knowledge is not solid enough, the implementation of integrated curriculum will be more difficult. Therefore, teachers should strengthen students' theoretical knowledge in a timely manner in combination with the actual working situation during the implementation of integrated curriculum. Teachers should strive to turn students' "weariness of learning" into "joy of learning" and "want me to learn" into "I want to learn". The integrated teaching itself teaches, learns, does is an organic whole, has the extremely strong attraction, may cause the student to study both and in the play, thus arouses the student's enthusiasm. Therefore, the competitive mentality of young people can be used to adopt group competition. According to the actual situation of the students, the group leader and team members are selected. Make full use of modern teaching methods and means to create skills competition or work practice situation to attract students to participate actively; In the integrated course teaching innovation and practice, teachers should explore a set of practical and effective teaching mode suitable for the students of this school.

V. Evaluation strategy of integrated curriculum

In the process of implementing the integrated curriculum in vocational colleges, a scientific and effective evaluation system is needed to make a comprehensive, systematic and objective evaluation and analysis of the teaching quality, so as to understand the advantages of this teaching mode and the problems in its practical application and improve it so that it can be better applied. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a multi-level educational evaluation system based on the deficiencies of traditional teaching quality evaluation, such as too single evaluation method and insufficient diversification of evaluation subjects, so as to improve the quality of teaching evaluation and the utilization rate of teaching results, and make it an important basis for teaching improvement, and make contributions to the curriculum

reform of vocational colleges. The following aspects of evaluation method, evaluation content, evaluation form and other aspects of integrated curriculum evaluation method proposed innovative reform measures.

1.Evaluation content

In terms of content, the integrated curriculum evaluation of vocational colleges should pay attention to the process performance of students in theoretical learning and practical training, fully consider the personality characteristics of students and the reality of social development, and enhance the timeliness, suitability and foundation of the evaluation content.

2.Evaluation method

The integrated curriculum of vocational colleges should combine the actual development of enterprises and students, and adopt personalized and diversified evaluation methods, so as to make the evaluation results more comprehensive and authoritative. Integration of teachers can adopt the evaluation methods mainly include the following: first, the real combination evaluation method, combining theory study and post practice, through the post practice let the students use their professional skills to solve practical problems, both can examine students professional skills to master degree and can exercise the student ability, achieve the goal of the assessment and evaluation of teaching quality. For this reason, teachers should create more opportunities for students to enter the enterprise practice in teaching, let students use their professional skills to solve some practical problems, so that students form professional pride, produce a sense of achievement, and further stimulate their interest in learning. Of course, the combination of truth and reality can be used to check students' mastery of professional knowledge, professional skills and post ability through practical activities, which directly reflects students' problems and objectively reflects the teaching quality. Second, the

project cooperation evaluation method. The integrated teacher sets a project, and the class students complete it in groups and report it after completion, which serves as one of the evaluation bases. The competition mechanism is introduced in the project cooperation assessment and evaluation to stimulate students' desire to win and actively explore. By introducing this evaluation method into the integrated teaching of truth and reality, students' professional skills and post ability can be comprehensively assessed, their comprehensive application ability can be understood, and their comprehensive potential can also be fully tapped. Third, Objective propulsion evaluation method. That is to say, teachers should grasp the overall situation of the students ahead of time, a comprehensive understanding of the students' basic knowledge, professional skills and practical ability, design different stages for different students learning objective, through timely inspection acceptance method, evaluate students each stage target completion, in order to grasp the quality of teaching, find the problems existing in the students' learning in a timely manner. Using this teaching quality evaluation method can not only grasp the teaching quality in time, but also improve students' vocational ability quickly.

3.Evaluation form

Integration should strengthen students post ability and professional skills, adopting diversified forms of evaluation, such as preschool education professional skills contest, which incorporates the idea of skill contest in practical teaching, encourage students to actively participate in various skills contest, making skills contest requirements to evaluate the quality of the teaching guide, promote the improvement of students' comprehensive professional quality.

VI.The conclusion

Integration of curriculum development and

implementation in today's society is the direction of the vocational education reform, practice has proved that the integration of curriculum development and practice made more significant achievements, the students would be able to obtain employment and the ability to quickly adapt to the professional role, teachers' enterprise practical ability and theoretical teaching ability have been greatly improved, the overall teaching quality of the school has been improved, and the social influence has been enhanced. The integrated course combines theory learning with practice learning. Through purposeful work pages, students' interest in learning is greatly enhanced. Through group discussion, the ability of students to raise questions, make decisions and solve problems in the team has been improved, and a batch of qualified talents with good emotional attitude, solid theoretical knowledge and professional ability have been cultivated for the enterprise and social and economic development. In the future, we should continue to promote the exploration and practice of integrated curriculum so as to better serve the sustainable development of students, enterprises and social economy.

Curriculum is the core of all kinds of education and teaching activities at all levels. It is the key to the reform of higher vocational education to cultivate students' vocational core competence through the reform of curriculum system. In the implementation of the "student center, competence-based, work-integrated learning" concept of modern vocational education and carry out effective teaching under the background of the integration course, scientific rigour to carry out the teaching design, is to ensure that the classroom becomes "useful, interesting and effective" "three" classroom, ensure the realization of teaching goal, promote the education teaching quality improvement, finally realize the key to the personnel training goal. Integrated curriculum is a new teaching mode in line with social development, which is not only conducive to the cultivation of students' ability, but also the demand of the market and enterprises for schools. However, as a new teaching and learning model, it still needs to be further improved in many aspects, such

as teachers, teaching materials, and equipment, evaluation mechanism, etc. The most important thing is the change in the concept of leaders and teachers in vocational colleges and the implementation of educational leadership in the reform from traditional teaching to integrated teaching. The solution of many difficult problems is a long-term process that needs further study.

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